

THE USE OF INTERNET SITES IN TEACHING ENGLISH

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Abstract: The global Internet offers opportunities for foreign language teachers to use many useful resources, distance-learning courses in teaching English. These are special programs for teaching foreign languages, as well as authentic materials that the teacher can select, adapt and use them for educational purposes.

Key words: global network, Internet, websites, resources, teaching English, intercultural interaction, computer technologies.

Аннотация: Глобальная сеть Интернет предлагает учителям иностранных языков возможность использовать множество полезных ресурсов, дистанционных курсов по обучению английскому языку. Это специальные программы для обучения иностранным языкам, а также аутентичные материалы, которые учитель может отобрать, адаптировать и использовать в учебных целях.

Ключевые слова: глобальная сеть, Интернет, веб-сайты, ресурсы, обучение английскому языку, межкультурное взаимодействие, компьютерные технологии.

One of the goals of using modern communicative approach in teaching foreign languages is to develop the ability of using foreign language in the process of communication as a form of intercultural interaction within the framework of human-computer interaction. Computer technologies became an integral part of the educational process and help language teachers in teaching a foreign language. Let us dwell on the following possibilities of computer technologies:

- 1) the use of a number of Internet sites in teaching English;
- 2) the use of Zoom, Google Classroom in teaching English;
- 3) students search for additional (to the textbook) information on the Internet under the instructions of the teachers;
- 4) search for additional (in relation to that given in the textbook) information by the teacher on the Internet for use in English classes;
- 5) the role of blogs in self-study of the English language.

The use of Internet resources in education already has rich experience as one can find the necessary information in global networks. There are a number of websites to solve a number of didactic tasks, which help for effective teaching of English: students can enhance reading skills and research skills using the materials of the global network, replenish vocabulary, motivation for learning English, expand horizons and develop communicative competence. These factors

require successful organization of independent work of students. For independent work of students, we can recommend the unique Internet site www.bbclearningenglish.net that is widely used in teaching English. This website offers all kinds of educational and methodological materials and allows the student to test his/her knowledge.

This website offers “Words in the News” section containing the latest world news in the form of short reports. Students have the opportunity not only to read, but also to listen to write a report and work out vocabulary on the topic. In the section, “Related BBC Links” students can see a story from the BBC TV news on this topic. The Read More, Related Stories, and Related Internet Links sections provide additional information that broadens the student's horizons. Students have the opportunity to choose reports on a variety of topics from the “Latest Reports” section. Video Stories provide students to read and listen to the stories. Students have the opportunity to read the definition of each word. Then the announcer reads the report against the background of the video sequence. The student listens to the report again and see the active vocabulary on the screen as it appears in the text. Another section of the [bbclearningenglish](http://bbclearningenglish.com) website, which is very popular among students. This is a video course about English idioms. The video course introduces those who learn modern English to frequently used idiomatic expressions. A professional British actor talks about them. The video course consists of 32 lessons.

Lesson 20, for example, introduces idioms with the word “hair”:

- I let my hair down (I relaxed, gave myself a break);
- Keep your hair on (Do not lose your temper, calm down);
- I am tearing my hair out (here: I'm just crazy about this).

The actor explains the meaning and use of the idiom in a funny way. Students also have the opportunity to see the full text of the lesson.

As a result, the use of [bbclearningenglish](http://bbclearningenglish.com) website helps students develop the following professional competencies:

- have linguistic knowledge, including knowledge of the main phonetic, lexical, grammatical, word-forming phenomena and patterns of functioning of the studied foreign language, its functional varieties;
- have an idea about the ethical and moral norms of behavior adopted in a foreign-cultural society, about models of social situations, typical scenarios of interaction;
- have main discursive ways of implementing the communicative goals of the statement in relation to the features of the current communicative context (time, place, goals and conditions of interaction);

- have main ways of expressing semantic, communicative and structural continuity between parts of the statement - compositional elements of the text (introduction, main part, conclusion), sentences;
- have main features of the official, neutral and unofficial registers of communication;
- be able to use etiquette formulas in oral and written communication (greeting, farewell, congratulations, apology, request);

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